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DIVERSITY OF PAPILONID BUTTERFLIES IN THE INDIRA GANDHI WILDLIFE SANCTUARY, WESTERN GHATS, SOUTHERN INDIA

Introduction

Butterflies are among the most easily recognizable of all animals. They are instantly familiar and also universally popular. Their wings, unlike those of most other insects, are colorful, opaque and are of characteristic shapes. The development of color, the range, diversity, brilliance and the kaleidoscopic assortment of patterns exhibited by butterflies is unrivalled anywhere in the animal kingdom, except possibly by the birds. Butterflies are truly the “jewels of creation.” Butterflies are typically active during the day and because they are so skilled in flight they have achieved an almost world-wide distribution, though as with most animal groups (particularly cold-blooded ones) there is a greater diversity to be found in the tropics (Mathew, 2001). Unfortunately, butterflies are threatened by habitat destruction and fragmentation almost everywhere (Mathew, 2001).

India has more than 1,400 species of butterflies, 330 of them in the Western Ghats alone, and of which 37 are endemic (Krushnamegha Kunte, 2000). They are one of the important food chain components of the birds, reptiles, amphibians, spiders and predatory insects; sensitive to habitat and environmental change, butterflies act as health indicators of an ecosystem. Concern for butterfly conservation is growing apace as more and more people are becoming interested in these lovely insects, which, essentially, do no harm to the human race.

Among the Lepidoptera, the family *Papilionidae* contains about 700 species distributed throughout the world (Smart, 1975). One hundred and seventy species of butterflies were recorded in Northern Assam by Betts (1950). Best (1951) reported 70 species of butterflies from Bombay and Salssetter.

In the Indian Ocean region (including India, Pakistan, Ceylon, Burma, Andaman and Nicobar islands) about 1,400 species have been found, including some of the most beautiful in the world (Wynter-Blyth, 1957). Sathyamurthi (1965) has catalogued the butterflies of the Madras Museum with reference to their morphology and habits -- a very useful guide to the butterfly fauna in the southern states. Chaturvedi and Satheesan (1980) reported 140 species of butterflies. The Zoological Survey of India conducted several faunistic surveys in the unexplored areas of Silent valley (1979-80). According to Chaturvedi and Satheesan (1980), the Indian subcontinent alone has over 1,443 species of butterflies.

The Western Ghats is the “hottest hot spot” in South India, and needs urgent attention because of the high degree of plant and animal endemism, and the grave threats it faces. To avert the crisis, we need to prioritize and target conservation strategies and investments in the Western Ghats tract. The Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, part of the Western Ghats located in Tamil Nadu, is a varietal storehouse of economically important plants and animals. The Anamalais is rich in biodiversity and provides a wealth of genes, which has to be conserved. The forests of Anamalais are so rich that it continues to provide benefits and services, purifying and regulating water supplies, cycling nutrients, creating and maintaining soils, providing pollination, pest control, habitat and refuge. It also provides tourism education, recreation and a livelihood to the tribals within.

Extensive studies on butterflies of Western Ghats, Southern India, were carried out by Goenkar (1996), including the first study that took into account of all 330 species in 166 genera, belonging to 5 families, recorded from this mountain range

and the adjacent areas. An intensive survey of Nilgiris and its environs by Gunathilagaraj *et al.* (1997) revealed 104 species of butterflies. The butterflies of Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary were listed in the management plan of the sanctuary for the first time in 1997 by Krishnakumar (1997). The diversity and habitat utilization of butterflies in different forest types of Hosur forest division of Southern India, was documented by Kathikeyan (1998). The diversity of butterflies in the sacred groves of Nagapattinam and Thanjavur districts of Southern India, was studied by Vasuki (2000).

Swallowtails are classified into only three subfamilies: the Baroniinae with a single species endemic to Mexico, the Parnassinae (Apollo

1. Southern Birdwing
2. Common Rose
3. Crimson Rose
4. Common blue bottle
5. Tailed jay
6. Lime
7. Red Helen
8. Common marmon
9. Blue marmon
10. Common bonded peacock

Troides minos
Pachliopta aristolochiae
Pachliopta hector
Graphium sarpendon
Graphium agamemnon
Papilio demoles
Papilio helenus
Papilio polytes
Papilio polymnestor
Papilio crino

Diversity of butterflies

Counting of butterflies was carried out in five chosen forest types, namely dry deciduous forest, moist deciduous forest, evergreen forest, scrub and thorny forest and teak plantation (mono-culture). In each forest type, two transects were laid across the habitat, so as to cover all features of the habitats. The length of each transect was 2 km. Butterflies were observed up to 20 m on both sides of the transects. Observations were made for the entire transects (2,000 m). The transects were away from the influence of edges and ecotones and well within the vegetation types. Places which were areas of major disturbances were avoided.

In the 2 km transect line, the ten selected Papilionid species were counted. Ocular observations were made. The key characters used for identification were color pattern, wing span, mode of flight, etc. No collecting of specimens was done. During the

butterflies) with approximately 50 species and the *Papilioninae* with about 650 species. *Papilioninae* alone occurs in peninsular India. However, its taxonomy is a little complex with many tribes, groups and distinct sub species. A simple description of Swallowtails, which are represented in peninsular India, was given by Kunte (2000).

In view of the foregoing account, in the present study an attempt has been made to study the bio-ecology of 10 selected species of *Papilionidae* in the Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary viz.:

study, flight patterns, activity patterns and behavior were also noted. The interaction of the butterflies with larval and adult host plants was also observed. The observations were made between 7 and 10 a.m. for a period of 3 years from August 1999 to July 2002, covering the four seasons viz., winter (December, January, February), summer (March, April and May), southwest monsoon season (June, July and August) and northeast monsoon season (September, October and November). The larval and adult host plants were also monitored and recorded. All the ten species of Papilionid butterflies chosen for the study were counted in different months and seasons. During the counts, their perpendicular distances from the transect lines and the heights at which they were seen first, as well as the date, time, and general weather conditions were also recorded. Densities of butterflies were calculated and the density/km² was arrived at as follows:

$$\text{Density} = \text{No. of Butterflies} / 2 * \text{Length} * \text{Width (of the transect)}.$$

Observations and results

Seasonal variations in butterfly diversity in various habitats

1. Evergreen forest

Seasonal variations in the densities and diversities of the 10 Papilionid butterfly species in the evergreen forest is given in Table 1.1. In the evergreen forest *T. minos*, *P. demoles*, *G. agamemnon*, *P. polytes*, *P. polymnestor*, *P. crino*, were found in all the seasons of year. *P. aristolochiae* was found only during the southwest monsoon and northeast monsoon, with higher densities during the former. *G. sarpendon* was found only during the northeast monsoon. *P. helenus* was found during southwest monsoon and *P. hector* was not found at all in evergreen forest.

2. Moist deciduous forest

In the moist deciduous forest *P. aristolochiae*, *P. hector*, *G. sarpendon*, *P. polytes*, *P. polymnestor* and *P. crino* were found in all the seasons. *G. agamemnon*, *P. demoles* and *P. helenus* were totally absent in all the seasons. (Table 1.2)

3. Dry deciduous forest

In dry deciduous forest *T. minos*, *P. aristolochiae*, *G. sarpendon*, *P. polytes*, and *P. polymnestor* were found in all the seasons. *P. hector* was absent in the summer. *G. agamemnon* was present in the southwest monsoon, while *P. demoles* was found in the summer. *P. helenus* was absent in the winter and the southwest monsoon. *P. crino* was absent in the summer. (Table 1.3)

4. Scrub jungle

In the scrub jungle *T. minos*, *P. aristolochiae*, *P. hector* and *P. polytes* were present in all seasons. *G. sarpendon*, *P. helenus* and *P. demoles* were absent in all seasons. *P. polymnestor* was absent in the northeast monsoon and *P. crino* was absent in the southwest monsoon. *P. agamemnon* was present only in winter (Table 1.4)

5. Teak plantation

In the teak plantation *P. aristolochiae*, *G. sarpendon*, *P. polymnestor*, *P. crino* and *P. hector* were present in all the seasons, while *P. demoles*

and *P. polytes* were absent in all the seasons. (Table 1.5).

Correlation between vegetation features and butterfly density

There was a correlation between the vegetation characteristics features in different habitats of Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, Anamalais, Southern India. Host plant density and diversity were found to be the most important variables that influenced the butterfly densities significantly ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

Seasonal variations in the diversity of butterflies among habitats

The density and diversity of treetop fliers like *T. minos* can be disturbed because of patchiness and fragmentation of forest patches. *T. minos* had the highest diversity in dry deciduous forest and scrub forest and relatively low diversity in moist deciduous and teak plantation. In evergreen forest the diversity was average. This proves that moist deciduous forest and teak plantation are not providing the needed environment for *T. minos* in the study area. *Pachiliopta aristolochia* is generally found in scrub and deciduous forest and its diversity was high throughout the study period in dry deciduous forest, poor in evergreen forest, and average in moist deciduous and teak forests. Its diversity was high in scrub jungle. *Pachiliopta aristolochia* is found to thrive in all the habitats. *Pachiliopta hector* is found in lower elevations and is abundant in late monsoon and winter. It is a butterfly of dry deciduous forest and thick scrub. In this study its diversity in dry deciduous forest was average, in evergreen a lot less and in scrub forest, moist deciduous and teak plantation it was good.

Graphium sarpendon is a species of evergreen and semi-evergreen forests and it is also found along side streams. In this study, *Graphium sarpendon* had an average diversity in dry deciduous forest and poor diversity in evergreen forest, scrub forest and teak plantation and slightly better diversity in moist deciduous forest. *Graphium agamemnon* is also a forest butterfly found in the forest canopy

as well as near the ground. In the study it was found that its diversity was poor in the dry deciduous forest, scrub forest, moist deciduous forest and teak forest, while in the evergreen forest the diversity was higher. *Papilio demoleus* is a butterfly of the evergreen forest found during the monsoon and post monsoon seasons. It prefers herbs and thickets of *Lantana* and is lured by citrus plants. This species had a poor diversity in dry deciduous forest, scrub jungle, moist deciduous forest and teak plantation, while in the evergreen forest the diversity was comparatively good. *Papilio helenus* had a poor diversity in evergreen, scrub, moist deciduous and teak plantation, while in dry deciduous it had higher diversity. *Papilio polytes* is well accustomed to human habitations and it is found in dry deciduous forest, evergreen and semi-evergreen forest. In this study it had an average diversity in dry deciduous forest, evergreen forest and teak plantation, while its diversity was high in scrub and moist deciduous forest. *Papilio polymnestor* is a butterfly of the thicker forest and found along ecotones and edges. In this study it had an average diversity in all the forest types studied. *Papilio crino* had an average diversity in evergreen and dry deciduous forest, while it had poor diversity in moist deciduous forest, teak plantation and scrub forest.

The study has established that resources for Papilionids are available in abundance during the northeast monsoon and winter periods. As seen from this study, scorching summer and southwest monsoon periods are probably not favorable for the Papilionids when there is probably a resource shortage. The southwest monsoon generally has intensive rain coupled with moderate wind velocity, which is probably the reason why the Papilionids remain dormant and inactive during this season. Although butterflies are directly dependent on plants for larval and adult requirements, they do not use all resources equally and all plants are not used as resources. It seems that even though vegetation structure is important for Papilionid species diversity and density, climate seems to play a greater role in deciding the diversity and density. Among forest patches there is a change in the availability and composition of host plants, which also decides the butterfly diversity. This is probably one reason why moist deciduous forest and dry deciduous forest seem to be supporting more

butterflies than evergreen forest, which has the highest plant species diversity. Season-wise, forest type-wise studies reveal that species like *Pachiliopta aristolochia*, *Troides minos*, *Pachiliopta hector*, *Graphium serpendon*, *Papilio polytus*, *Papilio polymnestor* and *Papilio crino* are able to adapt themselves better in all the seasons compared to *Graphium augeamemnon*, *Papilio demoleus* and *Papilio helenus*, which are sensitive to small changes and fluctuations. *Papilio demoleus* and *Papilio helenus* have poor diversity throughout all seasons. *Papilio demoleus*, though a species found in more diverse habitats than any other swallowtail, and whose home range includes savannas, gardens and evergreen forest, has strikingly poor density in all the areas studied.

This study revealed that in evergreen forest, the diversity of butterflies was highest during the northeast monsoon, followed by winter. In the moist deciduous forest, the diversity of butterflies was highest during the northeast monsoon and southwest monsoon. In the dry deciduous forest, winter had the highest diversity, followed by the northeast monsoon. In the scrub forest, the northeast monsoon had the highest diversity, followed by winter. In the teak forest the highest diversity was in summer, followed by the southwest monsoon. Thus, butterfly diversity patterns do not show any season-wise fixed pattern in the various forest types. *Troides minos* had the highest diversity in winter, followed by the southwest monsoon. *Pachiliopta aristolochia* had the highest diversity in the northeast monsoon, followed by winter. In the case of *Pachiliopta hector*, the diversity was almost the same in winter and during the southwest monsoon, with the lowest in summer. *Graphium serpendon* had the highest diversity in the southwest monsoon. *Graphium augeamemnon* had the highest diversity in winter. *Papilio demoleus* had the highest diversity in summer, while during the southwest monsoon and northeast monsoon it was insignificant. *Papilio helenus* showed poor diversity throughout the year. The reason for this needs further monitoring and intensive study. *Papilio polytes* had the highest density in southwest monsoon, followed by the northeast monsoon. *Papilio polymnestor* is the only species which had the highest diversity in summer, followed by the northeast monsoon. *Papilio polymnestor* was found to have an average

density all through the seasons. *Papilio crino* had the highest density in winter. Winter and the northeast monsoon seem to be favorable seasons for butterfly diversity in Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary.

A comparison of butterfly diversity and vegetation characteristics

Similarly, the study made by Kunte (1999) on the correlation between foliage height diversity, plant species diversity and butterfly diversity showed that the increase in butterfly diversity was not linear with vegetation diversity. It increased from high elevation grassland through shrub savannah, teak plantation and deciduous forest and then dipped down in the Shola evergreen forest. In this study, butterfly diversity had the highest correlation with host plant diversity, followed by host plant density, herb density and foliage height diversity.

A tremendous field lies open in the study of Lepidopteran behavior. We do not know how far individuals normally travel, how much they move around or how much they are attached to particular places or territories (Munroe, 1959). The distribution of the studied Papilionids in various forest types needs further investigation. More studies are needed on where populations originated, their migratory patterns, the causes of variations in densities and diversities, colonization, individual behavior and activities. The effect of feeding on host plants and the effectiveness of Papilionid pollinators also need detailed studies. This study is just a beginning and paves the way for further studies.

In the light of this study, it is suggested that more intensive study on the population ecology and present distribution of Papilionids and all other butterflies are needed, including the basic environmental parameters required for their survival and conservation. A species specific ecology and conservation biology program, as suggested for the *Homerus swallowtail* in Jamaica (Emmel, 1990), is also essential for all Papilionids studied in this tract.

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Table 1.1: Seasonal variations in the butterfly density (No./km²) diversity (H') in the evergreen forest of Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, Anamalais, Southern India.

S.No	SPECIES NAME	SEASONS*			
		WINTER	SWM	NEM	SUMMER
1	<i>Troides minos</i>	12	3	12	11
2	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	0	62	3	0
3	<i>Pachliopta hector</i>	0	0	0	0
4	<i>Graphium sarpendon</i>	0	0	9	0
5	<i>Graphium agamemnon</i>	6	7	3	6
6	<i>Papilio demoles</i>	9	3	3	1
7	<i>Papilio helenus</i>	0	3	0	0
8	<i>Papilio polytes</i>	3	8	6	3
9	<i>Papilio polymenstor</i>	9	4	15	6
10	<i>Papilio crino</i>	12	14	6	6
	Total	51	104	57	33
	Diversity (H')	0.1947	0.3117	0.2292	0.1547

- *WINTER = Winter Season (December – February)
 SWM = Southeast Monsoon Season (June – August)
 NEM = Northeast Monsoon Season (September – November)
 SUMMER = Summer Season (March – May)

Table 1.2 : Seasonal variations in the butterflies density (No./km²) diversity (H') in the moist deciduous forest of Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, Anamalais, Southern India.

S.NO	SPECIES NAME	SEASONS*			
		WINTER	SWM	NEM	SUMMER
1	<i>Troides minos</i>	0	6	0	0
2	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	19	20	39	2
3	<i>Pachliopta hector</i>	50	18	56	20
4	<i>Graphium sarpendon</i>	19	7	6	9
5	<i>Graphium agamemnon</i>	0	0	0	0
6	<i>Papilio demoles</i>	0	0	0	0
7	<i>Papilio helenus</i>	0	0	0	0
8	<i>Papilio polytes</i>	45	23	45	29
9	<i>Papilio polymenstor</i>	19	19	6	15
10	<i>Papilio crino</i>	12	5	12	2
	Total	164	98	164	77
	Diversity (H')	0.2748	0.2975	0.2916	0.1926

*WINTER = Winter Season (December – February);
 SWM = South West Monsoon Season (June – August);
 NEM = North East Monsoon Season (September – November);
 SUMMER = Summer Season (March – May)

Table 1.3 : Seasonal variations in the butterflies density (No./km²) diversity (H') in the dry deciduous forest of Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, Anamalais, Southern India.

S.NO	SPECIES NAME	SEASONS*			
		WINTER	SWM	NEM	SUMMER
1	<i>Troides minos</i>	16	8	17	18
2	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	133	98	108	76
3	<i>Pachliopta hector</i>	58	10	8	0
4	<i>Graphium sarpendon</i>	24	13	8	2
5	<i>Graphium agamemnon</i>	0	1	0	0
6	<i>Papilio demoles</i>	0	0	0	8
7	<i>Papilio helenus</i>	0	0	25	21
8	<i>Papilio polytes</i>	16	26	25	18
9	<i>Papilio polymenstor</i>	8	1	16	18
10	<i>Papilio crino</i>	8	42	25	0
	Total	263	199	232	161
	Diversity (H')	0.6296	0.3805	0.5962	0.4111

* WINTER = Winter Season (December – February);
 SWM = South West Monsoon Season (June – August);
 NEM = North East Monsoon Season (September – November);
 SUMMER = Summer Season (March – May)

Table 1.4: Seasonal variations in the butterflies density (No./km²) diversity (H') in the scrub jungle of Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, Anamalais, Southern India.

S.NO	SPECIES NAME	SEASONS*			
		WINTER	SWM	NEM	SUMMER
1	<i>Troides minos</i>	31	19	19	15
2	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	75	90	82	88
3	<i>Pachliopta hector</i>	63	29	51	45
4	<i>Graphium sarpendon</i>	0	0	0	0
5	<i>Graphium agamemnon</i>	6	0	0	0
6	<i>Papilio demoles</i>	0	0	0	0
7	<i>Papilio helenus</i>	0	0	0	0
8	<i>Papilio polytes</i>	69	23	37	44
9	<i>Papilio polymenstor</i>	6	8	0	8
10	<i>Papilio crino</i>	6	0	6	2
	Total	256	169	195	202
	Diversity (H')	0.3368	0.3805	0.3601	0.4061

*WINTER = Winter Season (December – February);
 SWM = South West Monsoon Season (June – August);
 NEM = North East Monsoon Season (September – November);
 SUMMER = Summer Season (March – May)

Table 1.5: Seasonal variations in the butterfly density (No./km²) diversity (H') in the teak plantation of Indira Gandhi Wildlife Sanctuary, Anamalais, Southern India

S.NO	SPECIES NAME	SEASONS*			
		WINTER	SWM	NEM	SUMMER
1	<i>Troides minos</i>	8	9	0	6
2	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	68	65	58	82
3	<i>Pachliopta hector</i>	21	22	51	21
4	<i>Graphium sarpendon</i>	8	8	4	7
5	<i>Graphium agamemnon</i>	13	4	0	0
6	<i>Papilio demoles</i>	0	0	0	0
7	<i>Papilio helenus</i>	4	0	8	4
8	<i>Papilio polytes</i>	0	0	0	0
9	<i>Papilio polymenstor</i>	16	10	4	14
10	<i>Papilio crino</i>	4	1	8	2
	Total	142	119	133	136
	Diversity (H')	0.1016	0.25418	0.1724	0.2631

* WINTER = Winter Season (December – February);
 SWM = South West Monsoon Season (June – August);
 NEM = North East Monsoon Season (September – November);
 SUMMER = Summer Season (March – May)